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EOSC service and FAIR uptake strategy

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Detailed report of all actions taken to ensure the promotion of EOSC and FAIR uptake in the user communities.

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List of Acronyms

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC Pillar	Coordination and Harmonization of National Initiatives, Infrastructures and Data services in Central and Western Europe
EOSC Synergy	European Open Science Cloud - Expanding Capacities by building Capabilities
ERA	European Research Area
EXPANDS	EOSC Photon and Neutron Data Services
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FAIRsFAIR	Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe
HEI	Higher Educational Institute
MoES	Ministry of Education and Sports
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
ORDM	Open Research Data Management
OS	Open Science
PID	Persistent Identifier
PMB	Partner member board
RoP	Rules of Participation
WP	Work package

Executive summary

What is the focus of this Deliverable?

The focus of this deliverable is to provide a detailed report of all actions taken to ensure the EOSC and FAIR uptake in the user communities. In particular, the activities of how EOSC and FAIR principles were promoted through the EOSC Promoters network are presented. By using the analysis of the survey (WP2) the needs of different stakeholders were identified and EOSC promoters understood and acted accordingly for the uptake strategies and actions. The actions that were adopted in order to raise awareness on the relevant topics to the user communities of each country is described, as well as how EOSC promoters were able to successfully fulfill the task. Collaborations and synergies with other projects regarding this topic are also reported.

What is next in the process of delivering the NI4OS-Europe results?

The deliverable and progress are described in the project Annex-I. Detailed report of all actions taken to ensure the promotion of EOSC and FAIR uptake in the user communities are reported in this deliverable. A paper will be published in order to promote the work that has been done.

What are the deliverable contents?

This deliverable describes the actions of EOSC Promoters in detail. Furthermore, an analysis of the material produced is reported so that the EOSC and FAIR principles were successfully spread by the national EOSC Promoters. It also identifies points and sections where the collaboration with other projects was established in this topic.

Conclusions and recommendations

This deliverable presents the ways the initial plan was implemented and how the EOSC Promoters acted to ensure EOSC and FAIR uptake in communities in-line with the Annex-I - Description of Action [8]. Despite the fact that the initial plan was affected by the pandemic, the EOSC Promoters acted accordingly and many actions were implemented online and when possible by face-to-face communication with the user communities on national level. Furthermore organization of a lot webinars were organized, and material was created and distributed appropriately.

1 Introduction

Task 6.3 had as main objective to raise awareness for EOSC and FAIRness throughout the user communities directly involved in the project either as thematic service providers or as users. In addition, task 6.3 invested effort in identifying appropriate actions to widely inform stakeholders on the benefits of the adoption and use of EOSC and FAIR principles and policies.

This deliverable describes the implementation plan and the actions that were taken by the project partners in order to ensure demonstration of services integrated into EOSC as well as the understanding of the EOSC policies, FAIR best practices, access and usage policies, etc. This was implemented by face-to-face communication with the user communities on national level, organization of seminars and webinars where user communities were invited to join, and by distribution of related information. In addition, the EOSC Promoters, produced a lot of useful material of basic guidelines on what is EOSC, as well as explaining FAIR principles, incentives for joining the EOSC, incentives and rewards for supporting ORDM and FAIR. All the material above was translated in partners' local languages by the translation officers.

In this deliverable the presentation of EOSC and FAIR principles is made in order to make sure that definitions are understood. Furthermore, Section 2 provides an overview of the EOSC Promoters' role and the criteria used for the right people to be appointed as EOSC Promoters.

The Section 3 of this deliverable will focus on the uptake strategy that was decided to be followed and an extensive reference of the awareness actions that were taken by EOSC Promoters in order to achieve the goal of disseminating the necessary information to the right people and reaching as many local stakeholders as possible. In addition, after the identification of the needs for the production of training/informative material, and guidelines for different stakeholders in order to make sure that they get familiar with the terms, and philosophy of Open Science, FAIRness, EOSC vision and mission, the goal was soon achieved through the network of EOSC Promoters. In Section 3 this is presented together with the translation material created by the Translation officers of our project.

In Section 4 of this deliverable there is the reference to the collaboration schemas with other projects and groups.

In Section 5 the actions of the NI4OS-Europe Group of Experts on Metadata, Ontologies and Semantics are analysed.

Conclusions are summarized in Section 6.

2 EOSC and EOSC Promoters

2.1 EOSC

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹ is an environment for hosting and processing research data to support EU science.

The ambition of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is to provide European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes.

This environment will operate under well-defined conditions to ensure trust and safeguard the public interest.

The EOSC enables a step change across scientific communities and research infrastructures towards

- seamless access,
- FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) management,
- reliable reuse of research data and all other digital objects produced along the research life cycle (e.g. methods, software and publications).

EOSC ultimately aims to develop a Web of FAIR Data and services for science in Europe upon which a wide range of value-added services can be built. These range from visualization and analytics to long-term information preservation or the monitoring of the uptake of open science practices.

2.2 FAIR principles

The FAIR principles were coined as a term at a Lorentz workshop in 2014².

The data-intensive science for the facilitation of knowledge discovery by assisting humans and machines in their discovery of, access to, integration and analysis of, task-appropriate scientific data and their associated algorithms and workflows, was defined as one of the grand challenges. FAIR principles were published in 2016, in the article titled "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship" by Wilkinson et al³.

The authors intended to provide guidelines to improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of digital assets. The principles emphasise machine-actionability (i.e., the capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention) because humans increasingly rely on computational support to deal with data as a result of the increase in volume, complexity, and creation speed of data.

¹ EOSC (2018). Available at: <https://eosc-portal.eu/about/eosc> (Accessed: 20 December 2022).

² <https://www.force11.org/fairprinciples>

³ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016) doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18

15 principles and a set of 14 metrics⁴ have been defined to quantify levels of FAIRness described as follows:

Findable

The first step in (re)using data is to be able to find them. Metadata and data should be easily findable by both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential component of the FAIRification process.

1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.
2. Data are described with rich metadata.
3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.
4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

Accessible

Once the user finds the required data, she/he needs to know how they can be accessed, possibly by including authentication and authorization.

1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.
 - 1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.
 - 1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.
2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.

Interoperable

Data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, data needs to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.

1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

Reusable

The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimize the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.

1. Meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes:
 - 1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
 - 1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.
 - 1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

⁴ <https://github.com/FAIRMetrics/Metrics>

The principles refer to three types of entities: data (or any digital object), metadata (information about that digital object), and infrastructure.

2.3 EOSC promoters: profiles

As the engagement of stakeholders was considered essential for the implementation of the EOSC vision, NI4OS-Europe has set up a network of people active in Open Science who acted as the Open Science, EOSC, FAIR ambassadors at national level. To choose these people a list of criteria has been set so that the EOSC promoters meet these requirements. The list of criteria is listed below.

Criteria set:

- The EOSC promoter should have an extended knowledge on Open Science, Open Access, FAIR principles etc.
- She/he could be able to contact and provide useful support to all different stakeholder profiles – supported by the partner organizations.
- The EOSC promoter should have a role with high visibility in the relevant country which could enable her/him to contact stakeholders.
- She/he should be involved in related initiatives.
- The EOSC promoter should have good communication skills and proven ability to communicate to small as well as to large audiences.
- The EOSC promoter should participate in all train-the-trainers' events which are organized by the NI4OS-Europe consortium.

The crucial point was on one hand to identify the needs of different stakeholders and on the other hand to find the most appropriate way to provide all the necessary information and training according to their level of knowledge on the topics. It can be considered as a great challenge since many Member States were not familiar with the basic principles of Open Science or haven't established any policies or infrastructures for the support of researchers, funders etc; this was also identified from the results of the survey of WP2 of the project⁵.

For filling the knowledge gap, EOSC Promoters were ready to take actions for awareness raising activities as it was considered that direct communication and an active network of Open Science actors can play a crucial role in supporting the breakthrough of EOSC and FAIR in the region.

It was expected that all the EOSC promoters were people who have visibility at their national level and were able to engage the community; thus acting like ambassadors for EOSC and FAIR. Further training of the promoters was needed and provided. All the EOSC promoters participated in train-the-trainers' events which were hosted by NI4OS-Europe partners. The detailed and final schedule of the train-the-trainers events were presented in the deliverable D6.66. The EOSC-promoters received training on National EOSC

⁵ Biljana Kosanović, & Milica Ševkušić. (2022). NI4OS-Europe Stakeholder map, inventory, policy matrix update. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6118786>

⁶ Sonja Filiposka (2020). NI4OS-Europe Training report. Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7127852>

additional training in topics such as, FAIR, National EOSC promotion, ORDM and onboarding of services.

2.3.1 EOSC promoters: list

NI4OS-Europe partners were called to provide their input regarding people that have the knowledge and will be able to perform the role of EOSC promoter. In the table below (Table 1) as well as in Figure 1 the names and pictures of the chosen people are provided. People proposed were knowledgeable in order to make sure that they meet the transmission of knowledge to EOSC and further aspects of Open Science (knowledge on Open Science, Open Access, FAIR principles etc.) and that they were able to play this key role in the scope of our project. The task of EOSC promoters was to ensure demonstration of services integrated into EOSC as well as the understanding of the EOSC policies, FAIR best practices, access and usage policies, etc.

Country	EOSC Promoter
Greece	Zoe Cournia
Cyprus	Sylvia Koukounidou / Chrysovalantis Constantinou
Bulgaria	Todor Gurov
Croatia	Bojan Macan / Drazenko Celjak
Hungary	János Mohácsi / Ákos Lencsés
Romania (ICI)	Dragos Catalin Barbu
Slovenia	Dunja Legat
Serbia	Milica Sevkusic
Albania	Arjan Xhelaj
Bosnia-Herzegovina	Mihajlo Savic
North Macedonia	Sonja Filiposka
Montenegro	Lidija Milosavljevic
Republic of Moldova	Țurcan Nelly
Armenia	Shushanik Sargsyan
Georgia	Tamara Gvenetadze

Table 1: The names of the NI4OS-Europe's EOSC Promoters

Figure 1: All the EOSC promoters per NI4OS-Europe partner

Details about all the EOSC promoters can be found on the dedicated interactive webpage of this action in <https://ni4os.eu/eosc-promoters-in-southeast-europe/>. A screenshot of this webpage is provided in Figure 2. By clicking on each country, a visitor can see who the EOSC Promoter of that Country is as well as her/his bio.

Figure 2: A screenshot of the webpage dedicated to NI4OS-Europe EOSC promoters

3 Uptake strategy and actions

3.1 *Introduction*

The uptake strategy was initially designed to be implemented in two levels namely at national as well as at stakeholder level.

As the survey of the project analysis showed that same stakeholder categories share similar concerns and needs, and express similar requirements towards EOSC, across more or less all countries which participated in the survey, NI4OS-Europe uptake strategy had to consider the specific needs and requirements towards EOSC adoption arising from the different stakeholders involved in Open Science, in parallel to the horizontal country-level.

In addition, having in mind the different categories of stakeholders and their profiles, the training needs were expected to be formulated according to the survey findings for each category. Different level of training, and several aspects of Open Science were expected.

As possible tools and actions there was the consideration of the collaborations with other projects or the use of existing material. Face-to-face trainings and/or workshops, webinars or teleconferences and work on and support collaboration with other local actors were also some of the uptake actions to communities.

The provision and dissemination of the produced guidelines, position papers, promotional material and any other supporting material or the translated existing material was also another mean to spread the mission and vision of EOSC and all aspects of Open Science.

Unfortunately, our initial strategy had to be changed because of the pandemic of COVID19 which created serious obstacles mainly to the face-to-face approach and not only.

Thankfully though all the EOSC Promoters immediate reactions we were able to adjust and proceed with achieving our goals.

The actions of the EOSC Promoters can be summarized in the next bullet points:

- Face-to-Face communication.
- Organization of Seminars and Webinars.
- Distribution of basic training material produced by NI4OS-Europe.
- Participation in the efforts towards the establishment of National Open Science Cloud Initiatives (NOSCI).
- Delivering lectures on Open Science.
- Promote EOSC, and NI4OS-Europe in media.
- In general, to spread the words for EOSC and FAIR.

3.2 *Actions by countries*

A lot of activities were fulfilled in the 3+ years of EOSC Promoters network actions. In all the partner countries EOSC Promoters were highly involved in conferences, meetings, Face-to-face communication, Seminars and webinars, created basic training material, participated in the efforts for NOSCI establishment, provided lectures on Open Science, spread the word for EOSC and FAIR, made promotion in media (local and European level),

monitored the progress, produced EOSC incentives and other material and participated to EOSC Promoters' social media campaign.

In the next subsections we provide highlights from the actions of EOSC Promoters per country. The actions for each country are presented in alphabetic order.

3.2.1 Albania

The fulfillment of the EOSC Promoters mission in Albanian OSC is now part of the new Albanian Strategy of Research and Education 2021-26. In addition, they are also working actively in the WG for the new Law of Science in Albania that is expected to include an Article dedicated for Open Science. An MoU for Open Science with different public and private HEI's has been signed.

The main activities that took place in Albania and the EOSC promoter was involved during the project were mainly focused on training and raising awareness with actions such as the following:

- Presentation of the EOSC activities in the national conference for Research and Education Challenges, September 2022 organized from MoES.
- Presentation of EOSC in the F2F OpenScience event organized from MoES/NASRI and RASH in December 2022.
- Online Training with end users during 2021, more as 15 sections with the participation of 300-350 persons from more as 20 HEI's.
- F2F meeting during the whole project period with researcher and academia promotion OS and FAIR principles.
- Meetings with MoES and support on the policy development for OS making an integral part of Albanian Strategy of Research.
- RASH have developed a dedicated Webpage for OpenScience named Albanian initiative for Open Science: <https://ni4os.rash.al/en/>.
- RASH has prepared different brochures, leaflets and promotion documents for Open Science in Albanian language, <https://ni4os.rash.al/sq/media/materiale/>. Example of such material is provided in Figure 3.
- Interview for Open Science in the national TV, NEWS24: <https://www.balkanweb.com/luarasi-dhe-rash-marreveshje-per-shkencen-e-hapur-akses-falas-dhe-pa-kufij-ne-informacion-kerkuesve-shkencor/>.

Throughout the above activities more than 500 people were reached including academic staff, researchers, staff of public bodies and agencies.

Figure 3: Flyer in Albanian Language, promoting EOSC and FAIR, produced by the Albanian EOSC promoter

3.2.2 Armenia

In the case of Armenia, the idea of the Open Science was basically unknown to the Armenian scientific community. As a result of the EOSC promoter work, the idea became familiar to the scientific circles. Second, they have developed and signed MOU with the Science Committee of Armenia that enables them, the Institute for Informatics and Automation Problems of National Academy of Sciences of Armenia, to disseminate and promote Open Science and EOSC activities. More specifically the EOSC promoter with her team have been concentrated on the following activities:

- Organization of seminars (Figure 4) and workshops (in total 5).
- Participation in workshops, seminars and conferences (in total 3).
- Being interviewed once.
- Release of a number of small website publications (in total 10).
- Participation in policy development activities. This included 6 meetings with the management of Armenia's National Academy of Sciences, and Science Committee of Armenia with approximate of 700 total participation of local people.

Figure 4: The Armenian EOSC Promoter, Dr. Shushanik Sargsyan presenting a seminar on EOSC to graduate students

3.2.3 Bosnia and Herzegovina

In Bosnia and Herzegovina, the main highlight of the EOSC Promoter was making people actually understand what EOSC is and why it's useful for them. Most of the generic EOSC promotional material tended to emphasize the organizational aspects (structure, governing, etc) which hold little value for an average scientist. They have tried to simplify and illustrate in relatable terms (this means customizing examples for various groups as IT, GLAM and medicine have vastly different use cases for EOSC). They have also made sure that relevant politicians and policy makers actually understand the position and importance of EOSC in future EU projects and wider cooperation. They have also tried to illustrate the difference between it and commercial cloud providers/services as this was considered very important.

The approach strategy followed was face-to-face events (as the restrictions were being lifted and as everyone was very tired from video meetings). Events were organized with varying number of participants depending on the aims. For politicians and policy makers, there was the aim of less than 10 participants in order to have a more direct engagement and be able to communicate more freely. For wider audience (students, high school educators, etc) up to 60 participants per group. For university level staff and active researchers, they aimed at 20-30 which still provided a more direct experience, but also is more efficient to organize that in very small groups. For those that expressed the interest further follow-ups were organized.

Involvement in the drafting of new regulations regarding science and promotion of open science by relevant ministry was and still is in place. Printed material seemed to be of no interest at all for their audience so the approach of a promotional interview with public broadcaster was selected with success in terms of audience and viewers. In total the audience reached directly was in face-to-face meetings and promotions, approximately 25 politicians and policy makers, 200+ university/researchers, 120 educators.

Figure 5: Bosnia and Herzegovina EOSC Promoter Dr. Mihajlo Savic presenting EOSC in the Public TV broadcaster of the country

3.2.4 Bulgaria

The work at the national level of Bulgaria was focused mainly on awareness-raising EOSC objectives, currently there are some promoting the FAIR data principles, and promoting national/European repositories and portals for open science among Bulgarian OSC community through:

- Organization of trainings (2 trainings – for end-user and capacity buildings)- and participation in relating trainings on the national level in the above mention areas.
- Organization national dissemination events (3 national dissemination events) and participation in the workshops, conference, seminars and other events (in more of them with a presentation).
- Promotion on the NI4OS-Europe onboarding services including in EOSC portfolio and repositories among the Bulgarian OSC community.
- Promotion the NI4OS-Europe call.

- Dissemination of project materials (most of them after being translated in Bulgarian), newsletters, etc.
- Publication of the press release, and videos for NI4OS-Europe achievements in some Bulgarian internet media, social media of my institute, etc. Example is presented in Figure 6.
- Publications articles (4 papers during the project life).
- Demonstration of how to work Bulgarian services and partners repositories/services from NI4OS-Europe portfolio.
- Participation in meetings (as members of OS WG) with policy makers from the Ministry of Education and Science (MES), working to set up Bulgarian NOSCI.

With a total of more than 300 people as participants.

As the main highlights of the Bulgarian EOSC Promoter's actions 4 points can be noted

- Participation in the establishment of the Bulgarian NOSCI, entitled "National initiative for Open Data and Cloud Computing" (NI ODCC).
- Contribution with advice in some strategic documents, such as the National Open Science Plan – the main strategic document with regard to Open Science that outlines the Open Science vision of Bulgaria for the next five years (2021-2025).
- Contribution to sustainability of developing OSC in Bulgaria (currently some national funding institutions such as the National Science Fund of Bulgaria and the Ministry of Education and Science support projects in the area of OSC and Open Data);
- Based on the promoter's work Bulgarian OSC specialists are members of the EOSC task forces on the technical interoperability of data and services.

Figure 6: An article written by the Bulgarian EOSC Promoter Dr. Todor Gurov where he promotes, NI4OS-Europe as well as EOSC through the video created by NI4OS-Europe with subtitles translated in Bulgarian

3.2.5 Croatia

In Croatia, the EOSC Promoters were actively involved in raising awareness of EOSC among Croatian research community and policy/decision makers. This had as a result of introducing and provide knowledge to more than 500 people and 500 to 5000 through posts and/or e-mails. The coordination of activities conducted by the Promoter's institution. Accordingly, they were working on the establishment of the NOSC Initiative.

The biggest benefit of being an EOSC promoter in Croatia it was the recognition of expertise on EOSC and related topics from the local research community. As part of their activities as EOSC promoters, they focused on disseminating information about EOSC and related topics (50-100 posts/e-mails) and educating the research community on these topics through presentations at conferences and other events (approximately 10 presentations), as well as working on a draft for a national policy on Open Science through the participation in the NOSCI working group for policies. A glimpse from the actions of the EOSC Promoters is provided in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Croatian EOSC Promoter Draženko Celjak presenting at the conference SRCE DEI 2022 (<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/dei-2022>)

3.2.6 Cyprus

Cyprus was highly involved in EOSC Promotion since the beginning of the NI4OS-EUROPE project. With more than 40 activities (organized or participated with presentations) as EOSC promoter they were able to reach the local community of researchers, policy makers and not only with a proximity of more than 500 people attendance in local audience (example in Figure 8). EOSC Promoters were also highly involved to the NOSCI creation and the National policy revision and final approve and establishment. Furthermore, a huge contribution to the creation, translation and enrichment of Greek language Open Science material via webinars and collaboration with Greek OpenAIRE NOAD for promoting EOSC, NI4OS-Europe tools and other Open Science topics and aspects.

3.2.8 Greece

The major highlight of the local EOSC promoter work was to participate in the Research Data Alliance Working Group for COVID-2019 as a representative of NI4OS-Europe. She joined the RDA COVID19-omics subgroup and participated in over 10 meetings between March and May 2020 in order to 1) clearly define detailed guidelines on data sharing under the present COVID-19 circumstances to help stakeholders follow best practices to maximize the efficiency of their work, and to act as a blueprint for future emergencies, 2) Develop recommendations for policymakers to maximize timely, quality data sharing and appropriate responses in such health emergencies, 3) Address the interests of researchers, policy makers, funders, publishers, and providers of data sharing infrastructures. During these meetings, the EOSC Promoter highlighted the role of Open Science for scientific discoveries and faster access to technological breakthroughs. She also highlighted the role of EOSC and of the NI4OS-Europe regional project in building infrastructures for Open Science in Europe. The main focus was on raising awareness in several conferences and events through participation and giving interviews for the general public and publications. Indicative actions are the following:

- Plenary Speaker in the Opening Session of the 1st EOSC Symposium, 2019
- Prepared video for EOSC Secretariat for The Research & Innovation Days, Brussels, 2019
- Participated in the RDA Working Group for COVID-19 as NI4OS-Europe representative to create guidelines for data sharing (2020)
- Published two articles on Open Science in collaboration with Research Data Alliance (RDA)
 - DOI: 10.12688/wellcomeopenres.16378.1
 - DOI: 10.12688/openreseurope.13369.1
- One more paper on EOSC promoters is being drafted to be submitted in Open Research Europe
- Presented EOSC and NI4OS-Europe in the MOLSSI Workshop, New York City, USA, 2019
- Presented at the International COVID-19 HPC Knowledge Exchange working group (XSEDE and PRACE), 2020
- Interview with the Omikron3 TV show in ERT3, 2 June 2021
- Presentation at Central European Initiative - CEI (July) meeting (8 July 2021)
- Organized 2-day event Capacity Building Training event on RDM: NI4OS-Europe toolbox, Greece 2021
- Participated in EuroCC Workshop: "HPC for the Greek Health & Life Sciences Sector", 17 June 2021 and Presented NI4OS-Europe and NI4OS-Europe Covid-19 Fast Access Channel
- EOSC Symposium 2021 (15-18 June)
- Presented RoLECT in the "Rules of participation & PID policy" session
- Covered SEE region in panel for the Policy Task Force session
- Invited by EOSC Secretariat to present WP2 work in the "EOSC engagement mechanisms at national level" session
- Participated in the sustainability session
- Participated in EOSC-Pillar/NI4OS - Business Model Workshop (1 July 2021)
- NI4OS-Europe: Presentation at Central European Initiative - CEI (July) meeting (8 July 2021)

- Participated in Open Science Fair2021 (20-23 September 2021)
- Demo session presenting WP4 tools (RoLECT, LCT, RePol)
- Coordinated FAIR implementation workshop (“Moving from recommendations to supporting practical implementation byservice providers”) with FAIRsFAIR and project partners from CYI & UD
- OS policy TF workshop
- SouthEast Europe GEANT forum, participation with oral presentation: “The added value of EOSC for research”, 3-4 November 2021
- Training on Research Data Management: NI4OS-Europe toolbox and good practices at EOSC, 6-7 December 2021
- Setup and Creation of the Greek NOSCI and related actions
- Promoted onboarded services of NI4OS-Europe in over 10 multiple conferences and workshops
- Online NI4OS-Europe training event in Greece on developing FAIR and EOSC Skills, 2021
- NI4OS-Europe Open call training workshop, 2022
- ATHENA-RC / GRNET mobilized the bottom-up OS Task Force and organised meetings for the signing of the MoU and the creation of the Greek NOSCI
- Participated in Athens Science Festival 2021, 2022 and presented NI4OS-Europe

Considering the interviews and the many conferences the total number of people reached can be considered over 5000 people in total.

Figure 10: Greece EOSC Promoter Dr. Zoe Cournia and her team promoting EOSC at the Athens Science Festival 2022

3.2.9 Hungary

As a major highlight/contribution of the Hungarian EOSC Promoter actions the managing of an open science newsfeed and the organization of Open Science events, including national Open Science forums can be noted. In addition, the contribution in forming the National Position Paper on Open Science is an important aspect in which the Hungarian EOSC Promoter has been actively involved. In total 5 national open science forums were organized, 34 Open Science workshops in fall 2022, and multiple other events with a total number of around 1000 people (350 at OS forums, 370 at 2022 fall workshop series, and many others at earlier events). A screenshot of one of EOSC Promoter's online presentation in a workshop is provided in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Hungarian EOSC Promoter Dr. Janos Mohacsi presenting EOSC in the Networkshop 2020 - Annual educational, research user conference

3.2.10 Montenegro

Through the promotion within NI4OS-Europe project, Montenegrin EOSC Promoter with her team presented the main concept of Open Science, FAIR data and EOSC services to a wide research audience, but at the same time, they collaborated with the representatives of the Ministry of Science and Technological Development of Montenegro, thus jointly creating different national documents and studies in this area. Their promotion activities helped to incorporate Open Science in the upcoming Strategy of Scientific Research Activity (2023-2027).

A lot of promotional activities in which the EOSC Promotion team participated took place during the realization of NI4OS-Europe project provided as follows.

Disseminations events:

- Two dissemination events were organized. The first one was held in the frame of the 24th international Information Technology (IT) conference, on February 18, 2020, and the second one at the premises of University of Donja Gorica, which is NOSCI partner, on September 28, 2021, as combined (both f2f and online) event.
- The Ministry of Education, Science, Culture and Sports of Montenegro in cooperation with the Central European Initiative (CEI) and with the support of NI4OS-Europe EOSC Promotion team, organized on July 8, 2021, an online event on the introduction of Open Science in Montenegro. The event was organized in the context of Montenegro's presidency of the Central European Initiative (CEI).
- An EOSC Promotion team member has participated as a panelist at online RELAB Multiplier Event: Creation and publication of representative open educational resources, held in the frame EU co-funded RELAB (Repository of Open Educational Resources for Laboratory Support in Engineering and Natural Science) project (<https://relab.kg.ac.rs/>) on November 10, 2021, where NI4OS-Europe project goals and actions were also presented.
- NI4OS-Europe EOSC Promotion team members have organized a session dedicated to Open Science and EOSC in the frame of the festival "Days of Science and Innovations" (<https://www.daninaukeiinovacija.me/>), on October 02, 2022. The Minister of Science and Technological Development of Montenegro, Prof. Biljana Šćepanović, Ph.D., with her team, has also attended our session.
- UoM EOSC Promotion team plans to organize a dissemination event in the framework of the 27th International Scientific-Professional Information Technology Conference 2023 which will take place in Žabljak from February 15th until 18th. One of the announced conference topics is dedicated to EOSC and Open Science in Montenegro (http://www.it.ac.me/eng/display.php?id_l=2)

The Montenegrin EOSC Promotion team participated in the following training events:

- Online event (webinar) on October 27, 2020 – capacity building
- Face-to-face event for end-users at premises of Faculty of Electrical Engineering, UoM, on May 24, 2022

The Montenegrin EOSC Promotion team published the following articles:

- Translation of NI4OS-Europe Press release in Montenegrin language and dissemination achieved through four e-portals on March 10, 2021: [1], [2], [3], [4].
- Two articles were published in Newsletter of Erasmus DIGNEST project about Open Science in Montenegro and EOSC, in September and November 2022, respectively:
 - Open Science in Montenegro: (<https://dignest.me/#/newsletters/newsletter-volume-5>)
 - EOSC is here to stay (<https://dignest.me/#/newsletters/newsletter-6>)

Active support to policy development:

- One of the EOSC Promotion team member was a member of the team of experts, who created national strategic document related to Open Science, entitled "Programme of Implementation of Open Science Principles in Montenegro with the Action Plan (2020–2022)". This document was adopted by Government of Montenegro in June 2020.

- EOSC Promoter Dr. Lidija Milosavljevic, was engaged in December 2021 by Ministry of Education, Science, Culture and Sport to create a Feasibility study of national Open Science repository. This Study was completed in March 2022.
- One of the EOSC Promoter team member was a part of the team who worked on Strategy of Scientific Research Activity (2023-2027) in Montenegro, as a member who contributed in the part related to Open Science.

Through the dissemination events they also organized and participated and two training events, which reached about 200 people, and many people were reached through newsletters and published articles.

Figure 12: Participation of Montenegrin stakeholders at a seminar on Open Science given by the relevant EOSC Promoter

3.2.11 North Macedonia

In North Macedonia, the EOSC promotion activities were as various as possible: there were training events in the form of a series of webinars (3-4), awareness raising together with the NOSCI community establishment (4-5), a couple of interviews for the digital university press (4), support to policy development (3), the tv mini series (2 episodes), presentations to relevant bodies such as the inter university conference, university and faculty boards (4) reaching more than 400 if you take into account the TV series broadcasted on national level. Two of the abovementioned activities that can be marked as the top contribution in the EOSC promotion work in North Macedonia in terms of reaching to the most relevant and widest audience possible. The series of PhD webinars on the topic of OS and EOSC which were followed by more than 100 PhD students each. This was an excellent opportunity to bring the concept of OS and EOSC to local young

researchers. Another great initiative was the mini TV series on the topic of OS and EOSC which was developed together with the national TV house and is available for the general public.

Figure 13: An article on EOSC created by the EOSC Promoter of North Macedonia

3.2.12 Republic of Moldova

The national EOSC promoter of Moldova has been focusing on promoting and training through various channels about EOSC, Open Science and good practices of Open Science implementation. Moldovan EOSC promoter were highly involved in

- Organizing events.
- Organizing trainings events.
- Producing publications.
- Involved in discussions with decision makers and stakeholders.
- Development of promotional materials.
- Posting in social media posts.
- Distributing information.

Additionally, there was involvement on the organization and provision of training on various aspects of Open Science. Some of these topics included Open Science Policy, Open research data, Creative Commons, tools in scholarly communications etc. Examples of training activities in which the EOSC promoter has been involved include the following:

- Participation in the organization of the NI4OS-Europe National Capacity Building Training Event in the domain of Open Science for Moldova, September 24, 2020.
- Participation in the online round table "Open Access - building structural equity and inclusion" REM Consortium, National Library Association of the Republic of Moldova in collaboration with the Department of Communication and Information Theory of the Faculty of Journalism and Communication Sciences USM and the Scientific Library of ASEM, October 21, 2020 (<https://eifloamoldova.wordpress.com/>). The EOSC Promoter, Dr. Nelly Țurcan presented "Open access to facilitate research and information in the crisis time" (in Romanian).
- Involvement in Science Days, 3rd edition, National Library of the Republic of Moldova, November 6, 2020.
- Participation in the online round table "It Matters How We Open Knowledge: Building Structural Equity". The event took place during the International Open Access Week 2021 with the participation of the Association of Librarians of the Republic of Moldova, REM Consortium, RENAM, IDSI in collaboration with the Faculty of Journalism and Communication Science of Moldova State University, October 28, 2021. <https://eifloamoldova.wordpress.com/2021/11/02/masa-rotunda-online-accesul-deschis-conteaza-modul-in-care-deschidem-cunoasterea/>.
- Participation in the Communication and Information Theory Workshop at the National Scientific Conference with International Participation "Integration through Research and Innovation", Moldova State University, November 11, 2021.
- Participation in organizing the Event in April 22, 2021 (one communication) <https://renam.md/renamnews/evenimentul-national-de-diseminare-ni4os-europe-a-avut-loc-cu-succes-in-moldova/>.
- Provision of education training for researchers, university teachers and staff of Moldova State University, April 13, 2021 (46 participants). The training material focused on "Opportunities for Open Science".
- Participation in the information seminar "Open Science Tools for Researchers", May 20, 2021, organized by Moldova State University and RENAM Association in the context of Europe Days 2021; Event in May 20, 2021 (one communication) <http://usm.md/?p=4028>.
- Organization of the Event: NI4OS-Europe National End-Users Training Event successfully took place in Moldova <https://renam.md/renamnews/ni4os-europe-national-end-users-training-event-successfully-took-place-in-moldova/>, November 18, 2021.
- Participation in the International Scientific Conference "30 Years of Economic Reforms in the Republic of Moldova: Economic Progress via Innovation and Competitiveness", September 23 – 24, 2021. Moderation of the round table "New roles and functions of libraries in the development of virtual communication in the online environment" on September 23, 2021. <https://ase.md/conf30/>; <https://eifloamoldova.wordpress.com/2021/10/07/masa-rotunda-noi-roluri-si-functii-ale-bibliotecilor-in-dezvoltarea-comunicarii-virtuale-in-mediul-online/>.
- Organization of the Workshop - Implementation of institutional policies on Open Science within the project "Boosting engagement of the Republic of Moldova in Open Science: methodological and applied support", December 16, 2021. Within the above context the EOSC Promoter presentation: "Open Science in the Republic of Moldova in the light of international and national initiatives" (in Romanian) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qXfLE3WtTgg>.

- Participation in the 2nd NI4OS-Europe National Dissemination Event in Moldova, May 5, 2022. <https://renam.md/renamnews/al-2-lea-eveniment-national-de-diseminare-ni4os-europe-a-avut-loc-cu-succes-in-moldova/>.
- Participation in in the International Scientific Conference, 26th Edition "Competitiveness and Innovation in the Knowledge Economy", Section "CONTEMPORARY LIBRARIES: CHALLENGES, TRANSFORMATIONS AND PREMISES FOR DEVELOPMENT IN THE NEW SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONTEXT ", ASEM, September 23-24, 2022. The EOSC promoter presented "Skills and Competences for Open Science Practices". <https://conference.ase.md/conference-program/>.
- Participation in the 2nd edition of the national scientific conference "Open Science in the Republic of Moldova", organized by the Information Society Development Institute in partnership with the State University of Moldova, October 27-28, 2022.

Furthermore, the Moldovan EOSC Promoter, Dr. Nelly Turcan has been involved in the organization of the following events:

- Organization of the Workshop - Implementation of institutional policies on Open Science within the project "Boosting engagement of the Republic of Moldova in Open Science: methodological and applied support", December 16, 2021.
- Preparation, moderation and organisation of the workshop "FAIR Principles in Research Data Management", organized within the project "Boosting engagement of the Republic of Moldova in Open Science: methodological and applied support", Information Society Development Institute in partnership with the Technical University of Moldova, May 19, 2022. <https://idsi.md/deschiderea-datelor-sustinuta-si-de-guvern-atelier-management-date-cercetare;>
<https://www.youtube.com/c/IDSITV>
- In the context of the Europe Days 2021, the Moldova State University (MSU) in collaboration with RENAM organized the seminar "Open Science Tools for Researchers" on May 20, 2021. A screenshot from the event is provided in Figure 14.
- Organization of the 2nd edition of the national scientific conference "Open Science in the Republic of Moldova", organized by the Information Society Development Institute in partnership with the State University of Moldova, October 27-28, 2022.

Moreover, the Moldovan EOSC Promoter, has been involved in the following raising awareness actions:

- Project promotion and presentations during the national events: Disseminating information on FAIR Data and Principles, Open Science, EOSC, NI4OS-Europe at the National Trainings for librarians, February, 8-26, 2021; <https://www.facebook.com/nelly.turcan/posts/10217184062251667>, master program "Management of infodocumentary institution", 2nd year.
- Project promotion and presentations during the national events: Disseminating information on FAIR Data and Principles, Open Science, EOSC, NI4OS-Europe at the National Trainings for librarians, March, 11-31, 2021; April 5-28, 2021; May 15-22, 2021 <https://www.facebook.com/formareprofesionala.usm>.
- Training for librarians within the retraining program at Moldova State University, December 12-13, 2022 (22 participants)
- As part of the project "Boosting engagement of the Republic of Moldova in Open Science: methodological and applied support" (2021-2022), the project team of the Information Society Development Institute coordinated by the EOSC Promoter made visits to transfer know-how on national policies and institutional strategies related to Open Science <https://idsi.md/ateliere-sd-balti-cahul>

The Moldovan EOSC promoter has been involved in the following interview

- Within the project "Boosting engagement of the Republic of Moldova in Open Science: methodological and applied support" (Information Society Development Institute) semi-structured interview was used for gathering information from key informants who have personal experiences, attitudes, perceptions and beliefs related to the topic of interest. A total number of 9 key informants were selected based on their willingness and the fact that they have knowledge and first-hand implication in the Open Science Movement, and considering their existing interest and involvement in Open Science discussions and practices, and their availability for the study. Most of these participants came from organizations that develop policies and manage projects related to Open Science (i.e. National Agency for Research and Development, The Academy of Sciences of Moldova, National Agency for Quality Assurance in Education and Research, The Court of Accounts of the Republic of Moldova, Moldova State University, Technical University of Moldova, State Agrarian University of Moldova, "Nicolae Testemitanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Institute of Legal, Political and Sociological Research).

Moldovan EOSC Promoter has also published a number of articles:

1. JURCAN, Nelly, CUCIUREANU, Gheorghe, CUJBA, Rodica, Lupu, VIORICA, CHERADI, Natalia, COJOCARU, Igor. Perception of Open Science in the Scientific Community of the Republic of Moldova. In: Postmodern Openings. 2022, Volume 13, Issue 4, 294-334. <https://doi.org/10.18662/po/13.4/519>.
2. JURCAN, Nelly; COJOCARU, Igor. Agenda Științei Deschise în Republica Moldova: politici și acțiuni naționale. In: Știința Deschisă în Republica Moldova. Ediția 2, 27-28 octombrie 2022, Chișinău. Chișinău: "Print-Caro" SRL, 2022, pp. 13-60. ISBN 978-9975-3564-0-4. <https://doi.org/10.57066/sdrm22.01>.

Dr Nelly Turcan has actively supported policy development in the area Open Science in the following actions:

- Submission from the Information Society Development Institute of the project "Boosting engagement of the Republic of Moldova in Open Science: methodological and applied support". The project was accepted for funding for a one year (September 1, 2021 - December 31, 2022). <https://ancd.gov.md/ro/content/rezultatele-expertizei-pentru-expresiile-de-interes-din-%E2%80%9Eoferta-de-solu%C8%9Bii-privind>.
- Discussions with Aliona Onofrei, interim head of the Policy Department in the field of research and innovation from the Ministry of Education and Research on the topic of the National Policy on Open Science in the Republic of Moldova, July 16, 2021.
- Discussion meeting with Adriana Filip - Solutions Consultant and Massimiliano Carloni - Country Account Manager from Clarivate Web of Science on Moldavian research output and Open Access data, providing by Clarivate Web of Science, June 24, 2021.
- Participation in the working meeting to discuss the report "Principles of Open Science in the Republic of Moldova" prepared by the expert Mr. Răzvan Valentin Florian. The meeting was attended by representatives of the Ministry of Education and Research (Aliona Onofrei, Head of Research and Innovation Policy Department, Iulia Vacarenco and Olga Duhlicher, Senior Consultants, Research and Innovation Policy Department), and Dr. Igor Cojocaru, Director of the Information Society Development Institute. The meeting took place on November 29, 2021.

- Organizing and participation in the working meeting to discuss carrying out projects within the expression of interest in "Offering solutions to promote the concept of Open Science and the development of digital technologies in the fields of research and innovation" (2021-2022), February 21, 2022; <https://idsi.md/sedinta-proiecte-os>.
- Contribution to THE CONCEPT OF THE STRATEGIC DOCUMENT REGARDING OPEN SCIENCE IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA UNTIL 2030, sent to the Ministry of Education and Research of the Republic of Moldova on behalf of the Information Society Development Institute.

Finally, the Moldovan EOSC Promoter, coordinated the production of the following training material:

- Developing and implementing institutional Open Science policies: Guidelines for research organizations.
- Developing and implementing institutional policies on research data management: Guidelines for research institutions

Through training activities, promotion, organization of events, a total number of more than 500 people was reached.

Figure 14: The presentation "Development of Open Science Policies at National and Institutional Level" at the information seminar "Open Science Tools for Researchers", May 20, 2021, organized by Moldova State University and RENAM Association in the context of Europe Days 2021

3.2.13 Romania

In Romania the major contribution of the EOSC Promoter was the opportunity to address various categories of stakeholders with relevance for each of them awareness increasing messages:

- For research performing organizations (including SMEs and large industrial companies): the available offer of EOSC services and infrastructure resources, as well as associated participation rules;
- For potential service providers: the overall EOSC core architecture evolution and on-boarding requirements, including the support they may benefit from the NI4OS-Europe project in getting acquainted with this technical ecosystem;
- For policy makers involved in finalizing RDI national strategic and planning documents for the next period: the strategic view at the European level on the EOSC priority as crucial research infrastructure objective as well as the current collaborative EOSC governance solution.

A special target audience has been the RO-NOSCI membership, including representatives of all above mentioned categories of stakeholders, which were the subject of the main flow of promotional news.

The promotional policy of the Romanian EOSC Promoter has been to take every opportunity to address an audience potentially interested in the subject. The result was a variety of activities both organized by NI4OS-Europe Romanian partners and events they were invited to participate in. Their activities were organized either within the NI4OS project (national dissemination and training events) or under the RO-NOSCI auspices (e.g. general assembly meetings). Also, they participated in different workshops organized by the Authority for Romanian Digitalization or by different Universities.

On support to policy development, the Open Science Knowledge Hub România (Figure 15), UEFISCDI had the main contribution to the development, under the coordination of the Ministry for Research, Innovation and Digitalization and with the consultation of other nation-wide experts, of the strategic document regarding the Open Science Development Framework in Romania entitled "The White Paper of the Transition to Open Science (2022-2030)".

Major promotional support was provided by the social media channels and websites of UEFISCDI and ICI, and more recently by the National portal dedicated to Open Science, administrated by UEFISCDI, which links the visitors to a plethora of EOSC-related materials.

Overall, we may count one major policy document, seven aware rising dissemination events, two training events, 4 papers in ISI journals, all NI4OS materials translated into Romanian all reaching more than 250 local people.

Figure 15: Participation of the Romanian EOSC Promoter Dragoș-Cătălin Barbu, at the event "Open Science landscaping and strategic development in Romania", held on 10/03/2020 in Bucharest

3.2.14 Serbia

In Serbia the EOSC Promoter was heavily involved in the development and promotion of infrastructure for Open Science in the country and policy development. The most important contribution of the work as an EOSC Promoter was a growing community of researchers and librarians interested in Open Science. When the project started, there were a few unconnected individuals who had only started adopting OS practices. Now, this is more of a network, a community of practice, including a dozen OS champions among researchers and more than 60 librarians who readily attend webinars and training events about OS. In the latter group, there are about 30 repository managers, who are particularly interested in EOSC and infrastructure development and will certainly pursue these interests in the future. In a total more than 400 distinct individuals were reached.

The main activities were:

- Informal training and various kinds of presentations focused on awareness raising. The situation caused by the pandemic turned out to be favorable for this kind of activities, as there was the ability to reach out to a wider audience using online conferencing tools. As the EOSC Promoter had already been involved in training related to OS, it was easy to include EOSC and NI4OS-Europe in regular presentations, but there were also organized presentations dedicated specifically to the outputs of NI4OS and EOSC Portal. During the project, the EOSC Promoter took part (as a speaker) in more than 100 events (mostly online) for instance look at Figure 16.
- Involved in the organization of two editions of Open Science Days, the most important OS conference in Serbia, and all national N4OS-Europe events.
- Involved in policy development on the national level, as a member of the working group who prepared the draft of the new national OS platform. Also supported the development of six institutional policies (as a consultant).

Figure 16: Serbian EOSC Promoter Ms. Milica Sevkusic presenting EOSC in a webinar

The most important materials that were produced to support the EOSC Promoter’s activities include:

- the timeline of policy development and repository development in Serbia: <https://time.graphics/line/314977>
- the map of repositories in Serbia: https://umap.openstreetmap.fr/en/map/repositories-in-serbia_701341#13/44.7738/20.5158
- the new website for the National Open Science Portal (some content had already existed; transferred it to a new platform, edited and adjusted it): <https://open.ac.rs/>

All presentations made during the project are publicly available.

3.2.15 Slovenia

In Slovenia the main actions were focused on representation of EOSC and NOSCI-related interests as member of the open science working group for the new Research and Innovation of Slovenia 2021-2030 and related action plan and provided input for the new Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act. Another highlight is the participation to the establishment of the Slovenian Open Science Community (Slovenian NOSCI), supported by the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation. Among other actions there were regularly provided training and presentations for faculty staff, librarians and PhD students on Open Science, Open Access and RDM and EOSC at an institutional as well as national level. Co-organized 2 NI4OS-Europe dissemination events and 2 NI4OS-Europe training events. Organization of a week-long international summer school course University of Maribor Open Science Summer School. Participation in the dissemination of open science and EOSC-related news via the NOSCI mailing list (ca. 180 members) and website (ca. 60 posts). It is expected that more than 500 local people were reached. In Figure 17 we present the advertisement flyer of the PUBMET2020 in which the Slovenian EOSC Promoter represented EOSC.

Figure 17: Advertisement of the PUBMET2020 in which the Slovenian EOSC Promoter representing EOSC

Accordingly, the EOSC Promoters network met bimonthly to report and exchange ideas and best practices, share challenges, difficulties and possible solutions. All the EOSC Promoters meetings hosted by the task leader as well as the WP6 leader are listed in Table 2. Throughout the implementation of this action, EOSC promoters received valuable experience and faced a number of challenges and obstacles which needed to be tackled by the appropriate activities. This effort as well as the experience gained is currently documented in an article which will be soon send to a journal for publication.

We have to also mention that the work of EOSC Promoters of NI4OS Europe had a major impact to all the country partners and it was a successful practice that other projects follows e.g. EOSC Pillar⁷.

Date	Main topics and discussion
15/01/2021	Action plans, Feedback for actions and Involvement in NOSCI & EOSC Association, Challenges of EOSC Promoters (Open Discussion), AOB
12/04/2021	Feedback from promoters' actions and Involvement in NOSCI, Incentives list for EOSC participation, AOB
16/07/2021	Feedback on EOSC Promoters page, EOSC Incentives list, website posts of our actions, Reporting of our actions, AOB
22/10/2021	Feedback on EOSC Incentives list translations, Website post of our actions, draft of our actions paper, review: comments and actions. Reporting of our actions, AOB
19/1/2022	Feedback on questions for our actions paper – next steps, organizing an activity for "The role of Young Researchers in Open Science, FAIR and the adoption of EOSC", Reporting of our actions, AOB
22/2/2022	EOSC promoters - discussion for actions paper Reporting of our actions, AOB
08/04/2022	EOSC Promoters actions paper - next steps, Reporting of our actions, AOB
15/6/2022	EOSC Promoters actions paper - next steps, Reporting of our actions AOB
12/12/2022	EOSC promoters' paper_ final draft version ready, highlights from our actions, AOB

Table 2: EOSC Promoters meetings and topics

3.3 Material created

Since the beginning of the EOSC promoters actions the need of the creation of informative material was identified. For that reason, three brochures were created and translated in local language to ensure the dissemination of specific topics was correctly provided. In addition, a fourth brochure was created within the scope of WP4, namely the "Incentives & Rewards for supporting Open Research Data Management and FAIR" which was also translated in the local NI4OS-Europe languages.

⁷ EOSC-Pillar Ambassadors Programme (2020). Available at: <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/ambassadors-programme> (Accessed: 20 January 2023).

The brochures were announced and provided during the activities and also uploaded to the NI4OS-Europe project website⁸.

3.3.1 Removing language barriers - Translation officers

As in several other cases, language can be a barrier also in the implementation of EOSC and the establishment of Open Science and FAIR principles in the partner countries of South Eastern Europe. Removing language barriers is especially important in case of activities where policies, guidelines, glossaries, training material, or similar documents need to be used, adopted or generated. NI4OS-Europe therefore decided to assign in each partner country a translation officer, who were responsible to translate documents that play a central role in the setting up of National Open Science Cloud Initiatives and in the promotion of EOSC and FAIR. The list of translation officers is shown in the table below.

Country	Translation Officer
Greece	Evangelia Athanasaki
Cyprus	Chrysovalantis Constantinou
Bulgaria	Nedu Karaivanov
Croatia	Kristina Posavec/Lovorka Caja
Hungary	Csilla Gödri
Romania	Ella Ciuperca
Slovenia	Brina Klemenčič
Serbia	Milica Sevkusic
Albania	Bledar Meniku
Bosnia-Herzegovina	Mihajlo Savic
North Macedonia	Bojana Koteska
Montenegro	Enis Kočan
Republic of Moldova	Natalia Cherady
Armenia	Naira Kocharyan
Georgia	Tamara Gvenetadze

Table 3: The names of the NI4OS-Europe translation officers

3.3.1.1 Quality check

To assure the exact translation of each document from English to the mother tongue of each partner state, the translation officers were responsible to share their documents with the partners within the relevant country. After the quality check, the documents should be returned back to the translation officers who were responsible for the circulation of the documents to the partner's stakeholders, task leaders, work package leaders, etc.

3.3.1.2 Translated documents

The documents which have been produced for the EOSC and FAIR promotion as well as have being translated to the mother tongues of the NI4OS-europe countries are:

⁸ <https://ni4os.eu/material/>

1. European Open Science Cloud – EOSC (EN)

Available in all mother languages of the NI4OS-Europe area via the project training platform (AL, AM, BA, BG, GE, GR, HR, HU, MD, ME, MK, RO, RS, SI). All the documents can be found in <https://training.ni4os.eu/course/view.php?id=52>. Examples of the title pages in Bulgarian, Montenegrin and Romanian are presented in Figure 18.

Figure 18: The translations of the document “European Open Science Cloud” in Bulgarian, Montenegrin and Romanian from left to right

Everything you need to know about FAIR Data

Figure 19: The translations of the document “Everything you need to know about FAIR Data” in Greek, Slovenian and Georgian from left to right

2. Everything you need to know about FAIR Data (EN)

Available in all mother languages of the NI4OS-Europe area via the project training platform (AL, AM, BA, BG, GE, GR, HR, HU, MD, ME, MK, RO, RS, SI). All the documents can be found in <https://training.ni4os.eu/course/view.php?id=52>. Examples of the title pages of the translation in Greek, Slovenian and Georgian are presented in Figure 19.

3. Subtitles in the NI4OS-Europe Video

The NI4OS-Europe Video is available in YouTube at the following web address <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M8LnlP3lNbo&t=11s>. One can choose subtitles in one of the NI4OS-Europe mother languages including English. Examples of screenshots with subtitles in English, Albanian and Armenian are shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Screenshots from the NI4OS-Europe video with subtitles in English, Albanian and Armenian

4. Incentives & Rewards for supporting Open Research Data Management and FAIR

Available in all mother languages of the NI4OS-Europe area via (AL, AM, BA, BG, GE, GR, HR, HU, MD, ME, MK, RO, RS, SI) soon via the training platform. Examples of the title pages of the translation in Romanian, Croatian and English are presented in Figure 21.

Incentives & Rewards for supporting ORDM and FAIR

Figure 21: The translations of the document “Incentives & Rewards for supporting Open Research Data Management and FAIR” in Romanian, Croatian and English from left to right

Figure 22: The translations of the document “Why Support EOSC?” in English, North Macedonian and Bosnian from left to right

5. How to support EOSC – Incentives List via the project training platform

Available in all mother languages of the NI4OS-Europe area via the project training platform (AL, AM, BA, BG, GE, GR, HR, HU, MD, ME, MK, RO, RS, SI). All the documents can be found in <https://training.ni4os.eu/course/view.php?id=52>. Examples of the title

pages of the translation in English, North Macedonian and Bosnian are presented in Figure 22.

3.3.2 Additional material

In addition, a Learning Path⁹ about EOSC and FAIR topics was also created and is provided through the NI4OS training platform. This learning path can be considered as the starting point for anyone who is interested to understand what EOSC is and how researchers achieve their goals via EOSV. It also provides all the necessary materials for a better knowledge of FAIR principles.

After completing this learning path, stakeholders are expected to understand what EOSC and FAIR data is, understand the fundamentals of EOSC and FAIR principles, be informed about developments on EOSC and FAIR and finally to understand how to implement FAIR principles and be involved in EOSC.

⁹ <https://training.ni4os.eu/course/index.php?categoryid=7>

4 Collaboration with other projects and participation in relevant Working groups

4.1 *Cooperation with FAIRsFAIR towards the FAIR uptake*

FAIRsFAIR - standing for "Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe" - is a European Commission project under the call H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020 with grant agreement 831558 aiming to supply practical solutions for the usage of the FAIR data principles throughout the research data life cycle. Within this project emphasis was given on fostering FAIR data culture and the uptake of good practices in making data FAIR. Thus, FAIRsFAIR is expected to play a key role in the development of global standards for FAIR certification of repositories and the data within them contributing to those policies and practices that will turn the EOSC program into a functioning infrastructure.

FAIRsFAIR also provided a platform for using and implementing the FAIR principles in the day-to-day work of European research data providers and repositories. FAIRsFAIR delivered essential FAIR dimensions of the Rules of Participation (RoP) and regulatory compliance for participation in the EOSC. The EOSC governance structure uses these FAIR aligned RoPs to establish whether components of the infrastructure function in a FAIR manner.

It is thus clear that FAIRsFAIR served as a scheme supporting the FAIR uptake for the whole Europe within the framework of the European Open Science Cloud. It would be therefore important for NI4OS-Europe to establish connection with FAIRsFAIR and directly collaborate towards the uptake of FAIR. With such a collaboration both projects could benefit and increase their potential to the overall uptake. In this framework the projects had signed a Memorandum of Understanding, including also other projects discussed below.

NI4OS-Europe initiated a direct communication with the project coordinator and the Work-Package 6 leader of FAIRsFAIR. WP6 of FAIRsFAIR was dealing with FAIR Competence Center and focuses on FAIR uptake - it is thus very relevant to the related NI4OS-Europe activities. The key tasks of this work package are: the support of communities in their activities aimed at FAIR data uptake and compliance, the promotion and coordination of efforts across communities, identifying opportunities for synergies and building on the progress of others, and finally receiving feedback from communities into other parts of the FAIRsFAIR project and the EOSC in generally.

Built on the successful Synchronisation Force series from the FAIRsFAIR project, a newly funded project FAIR-IMPACT will establish dialogue for collaboration and harmonisation with various projects, initiatives and actors in both EOSC and FAIR ecosystems to reduce redundancy and ensure that solutions are more widely promoted, sustainable and can be transferred to the relevant EOSC Partnership and current and future EOSC stakeholders.

An important aspect of the effort of NI4OS-Europe towards FAIR uptake in the region was the appointment of the translation officers as their actions are described in a previous section. FAIRsFAIR recognized the importance of being heard by all possible audiences all across Europe. Therefore, material which had been produced by FAIRsFAIR towards FAIR principles and other related topics were channeled also through NI4OS-Europe towards the local FAIR uptake. NI4OS-Europe used parts of such material and translated it to the local tongues.

Furthermore, another aspect in which both projects collaborated was the organization of training events. Namely, FAIRsFAIR has provided trainers on several topics which have been presented in train-the-trainer events. For instance, in the first train-the-trainer event which was focusing on "FAIR principles" and which was hosted on the 17th of January by the University of Debrecen, two of the trainers were data management experts coming from DANS which is participating in the FAIRsFAIR.

4.2 Cooperation with other INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019 projects

In addition to an initiative for a bilateral collaboration between NI4OS-Europe and FAIRsFAIR, a coordinated effort for the collaboration between FAIRsFAIR and other INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019 projects had been initiated by the European Commission focusing mostly on the sharing of experience between other INFRAEOSC-05b projects. The idea is to bring together the following projects to collaborate in a series of topics.

- **EOSCsecretariat.eu** ran from 2019-2021 and supported the Interim Governance of the European Open Science Cloud. It was a vital time for the development of the EOSC and the project supported the EOSC Executive Board and its Working Groups (WG) to pave the way forward for the now ongoing implementation phase of the EOSC and the establishment of the EOSC Partnership. All results from the Interim Governance can be found on this website including the first version of the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) and 20 recommendations reports. These are now being followed by the EOSC Association and its Task Forces which our project also supported.
- **EOSC-Nordic** worked towards facilitation and the coordination of EOSC relevant initiatives within the Nordic and Baltic countries. The project aimed to exploit synergies to achieve greater harmonisation at policy and service provisioning across these countries, in compliance with EOSC agreed standards and practices. EOSC Nordic ran the FAIRification initiative for repositories aiming to consistently integrate datasets, software, publications, and other research outputs for researchers. The way to do this is to adhere to the FAIR principles to make research data more reusable and science more transparent, efficient, and trustworthy. To achieve this, interesting cooperation and synergy between FAIRsFAIR and the EOSC-Nordic projects emerged where the EOSC-Nordic FAIRification team used and tested the automated FAIR evaluator (F-UJI) tool developed by FAIRsFAIR to measure the FAIRness of the repository's (meta)data. F-UJI is a web service to programmatically assess FAIRness of research data objects based on metrics developed by the FAIRsFAIR project. This website aims to demonstrate the application of the web service as a backend to implement a user friendly web application which allows the evaluation of FAIRness of digital research data objects (aka data sets).
- **EOSC-Pillar** co-ordinated national Open Science efforts across Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy, and ensured their contribution and readiness for the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The work of EOSC-Pillar is comprised of seven parts with majority working on a national and transnational level. EOSC-Pillar possibly influenced by the idea of EOSC promoters, released the

EOSC-Pillar Ambassadors Programme. This offers an information package to support everyone who wants to get involved in raising awareness for EOSC. The main difference of EOSC Ambassadors Programme is that this is on a volunteer base whilst EOSC promoters has been an essential element of the FAIR and EOSC uptake in the regions and consisted of skilled NI4OS-Europe members.

- **EOSC-synergy** contributed to the European Open Science Cloud landscape by expanding the capacity and capabilities of EOSC. In practice, this meant more compute and storage available to researchers, and more datasets and tools to expand avenues of research. The ultimate goal of EOSC-synergy was to build EOSC as a coordinated effort, as an open environment for scientific data and related processing that promotes convergence of infrastructures and scientific thematic services provided at national or European level.
- **ExPaNDS** is a federation of 10 European national Photon and Neutron research infrastructures, and the e-infrastructure EGI. The project has set-up a platform for data analysis, as a service for users from research institutes, universities, industry, etc, thus enabling EOSC services, and providing coherent FAIR data services to the scientific users of PaN sources. In the frame of ExPaNDS, partners maintained and developed a catalogue of data and analysis software for PaN data, and cooperated with the EOSC governance bodies to further improve the EOSC. Furthermore, they shared and exchanged the benefits of ExPaNDS with other clusters connected to the EOSC.
- **NI4OS-Europe** supported the development and inclusion of the national Open Science Cloud initiatives in 15 Member States and Associated Countries in the overall scheme of EOSC governance; spread the EOSC and FAIR principles in the community and trained it; and provided technical and policy support in on-boarding of the existing and future service providers into EOSC, including generic services (compute, data storage, data management), thematic (domain-specific) services, repositories and data sets – thus introducing new services that cover the whole spectrum of services related to Open Science, data and publications.

All the project described above share similar views on the FAIR uptake. Hence, a coordinated effort led by EOSCsecretariat.eu, namely the FAIR synchronisation task, is bringing the five INFRAEOSC-5b projects together with FAIRsFAIR and provides a stage for collaboration and common actions towards the uptake of FAIR in the whole European region. The WP6 leader, T6.1 leader as well as Elli Papadopoulou have worked closely within the FAIRsFAIR FAIR Task Force. The following mutual actions have been agreed upon as a starting point for collaboration:

1. Review and standardization of FAIR policies in order to enable FAIR-aligned services and repositories;

2. Analysis of FAIR guidelines and standards to enable adoption in the light of the local and disciplinary context;
3. Evaluation and development of FAIR technical aspects including metadata frameworks, interoperability, service infrastructure, FAIR software;
4. Assessment, extension or establishment of FAIR certification schemes for repositories and services. The uptake in communities and on national levels is of special importance;
5. Development and adaptation of FAIR assessment tools. These tools include, but are not limited to, DMPs, licenses and datasets.

4.3 Participation in the FAIR Task Force

The way FAIR Task Force facilitated its goals as through a series of meeting in which the members discussed their recent updates on the five above topics and initiated collaborations around these five pillars. A table with all the meetings which took place within the context of the FAIR Task Force is provided in Table 4.

#	Date	Main Topics of discussion	Contribution of NI4OS-Europe
1	September, 26, 2019	First meeting, introduction of the projects	Presentation of NI4OS-Europe
2	October 28, 2019	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
3	February, 4, 2020	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
4	March, 18, 2020	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
5	April, 20, 2020	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
6	June, 9, 2020	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
7	August, 25, 2020	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
8	September, 23,2020	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
9	October, 20, 2020	Cancelled due to lack of participants	
10	November, 25, 2020	Meeting with EC visitors to discuss the FAIR assessment and certification tools	Participation
11	January, 26, 2021	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
12	March, 30, 2021	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates as well as the ORDM tools developed within the project
13	May, 25, 2021	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
14	July, 8, 2021	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
15	September, 7, 2021	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
16	November, 4, 2021	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
17	January, 17, 2022	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.
18	March, 16 2022	Updates of projects.	Presented recent updates.

19	May, 18, 2022	Updates of projects.	Host of the meeting, and presented recent updates.
20	September, 13, 2022	Updates on projects.	Presented recent updates.
21	December, 5, 2022	Updates. Wrapping up as this is the final meeting.	Host of the meeting, and presented recent updates.

Table 4: All the meetings which took place within the context of FAIR TF

4.3.1 Highlights of the FAIR TF meetings

On Thursday 26th of November 2020 the InfraEOSC-5 FAIR data and infrastructure Task Force, set-up by the projects in the INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019 call: EOSC-synergy, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic, NI4OS-Europe, ExPaNDS, FAIRsFAIR, and EOSCsecretariat.eu, organized a special edition of the usual monthly meeting to present to the European Commission the key work which had been carried out on the topic of FAIR data assessment and certification tools by the InfraEOSC-5 call funded initiatives.

The event was co-organized by the EOSCsecretariat.eu and the FAIRsFAIR initiative and engaged all the projects actively involved in the FAIR Task Force with the aim to provide an overview on the tools, challenges, lessons learned and recommendations towards FAIR Assessment and certification of digital objects and data repositories. The meeting also gave a deep-dive into practical use cases that demonstrated the impact of applying the developed tools to different communities across Europe and the priorities for the stakeholders involved.

The produced report gathered the challenges and lessons learned as well as recommendations from the InfraEOSC-5 projects with respect to the activities undergoing on FAIR data assessment and certification in the EOSC region. The report can be found on the following link: <https://zenodo.org/record/4332408>

On Tuesday 30th of March 2021, the InfraEOSC-5 FAIR data and infrastructure Task-Force, meeting set-up a meeting in which NI4OS-Europe was given stage to present in detail two of the ORDM tools developed within the framework of NI4OS-Europe RePol and LCT. Namely, NI4OS-Europe WP4 leader Dr. Branko Marovic presented the ORDM tool Repository Policy Generator – RePol (<https://repol.ni4os.eu/>). In addition, Dr. Panagiota Koltsida presented the Licence Clearance Tool – LCT (<https://lct.ni4os.eu/lct/login>). The two ORDM tools attracted the attention and the interest of all the participants from all the INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019 projects and the scenario of testing the tools in use cases had been discussed.

Since hosting of the FAIR TF meetings had been a duty of FAIRsFAIR, once FAIRsFAIR ended, the chairing of the meetings had become voluntary. Hence, NI4OS-Europe chaired the 19th as well as the last meetings.

4.4 Collaboration with OntoCommons

OntoCommons is an H2020 CSA project dedicated to the standardisation of data documentation across all domains related to materials and manufacturing. It lays the foundation for interoperable, harmonised and standardised data documentation through

ontologies, facilitating data sharing and pushing data-driven innovation, to bring out a truly Digital Single Market and new business models for European industry, exploit the opportunities of digitalisation and address sustainability challenges.

By developing the Ontology Commons EcoSystem (OCES) - a set of ontologies and tools that follows specific standardisation rules - and provide a sustainable approach, making the data FAIR. Moreover, the OCES implements practical and user-friendly mechanisms of intra- and cross-domain interoperability focusing on materials and manufacturing sectors.

This will be achieved by coordinating a wide range of EU stakeholders and with the support of Demonstration Cases with strong industrial involvement, covering a wide range of NMBP (Nanotechnologies, Advanced Materials, Biotechnology, and Advanced Manufacturing and Processing) application domains.

OntoCommons represents relevant stakeholder knowledge by bringing together a consortium from a wide range of communities including subject matter experts (e.g. material scientists), ontologists (e.g. philosophers, semantic web experts), implementers (e.g. database experts), industrial end users (e.g. manufacturers), and application developers.

The existence of the NI4OS-Europe Group of Experts on Metadata, Ontologies and Semantics as well as its actions, which is presented in the next section, attracted the interest of other Horizon 2020 projects working on relevant topics. Namely, FAIRsFAIR initiated a contact between NI4OS-Europe and OntoCommons. This has led to a bilateral collaboration between the two projects which included the co-organization of several workshops.

4.4.1 KExS workshops

To achieve its goals, for OntoCommons it was essential to draw on already existing networks of (European) bodies, projects and initiatives with the objective of establishing a shared data documentation framework. Hence OntoCommons Initiated a series of workshops called "Creating a Knowledge Exchange Space for data management and documentation - KExS". The members participating in the series of KExS workshops are EOSC landscape stakeholders (EOSC Association, EOSC Association Task Forces, EOSC Future, EOSC Secretariat, EOSC-Nordic, EOSC Pillar, EOSC Synergy, ExPaNDS, NI4OS-Europe), FAIR initiatives (FAIRSharing, FAIRsFAIR, GO FAIR Foundation), and RDA (RDA Secretariat, Chemistry Research Data IG, RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG, Vocabulary Services IG).

The main objective of the first workshop was to build the basis for further cooperation between OntoCommons and projects related to FAIR implementation, EOSC infrastructure and data management good practices (Research Data Alliance). In the first workshop, which was held online on the 1st of July 2021, the project introduced OntoCommons to other relevant projects and started discussions on specific topics for collaboration i.e. FAIR principles, cross domain semantic interoperability and services and infrastructure. The NI4OS-Europe members participating in KExS is WP6 leader Dr. Andreas Athenodorou as well as Ms. Elli Papadopoulou. In the first workshop, Andreas Athenodorou, presented NI4OS-Europe to the participants.

The second KExS workshop took place online on the 22nd of October 2021. This workshop strengthened further the basis for cooperation between OntoCommons and projects related to FAIR implementation, EOSC infrastructure and data management good practices

(Research Data Alliance) as well as to decide on preferred work modes and the next steps to take.

4.4.2 KExS meetings

Followingly, the form of workshops transformed to monthly online meetings, with the first meeting taking place on the 11th of January 2022, the second meeting on the 8th of February 2022. The third meeting took place on the 8th of March 2022. In this meeting NI4OS-Europe hosted a webinar to present the NI4OS-Europe Group of Experts on Metadata, Ontologies and Semantics. This involved a presentation of the scope of NI4OS-Europe and its goals and the announcement of the webinar on "Community Support Discussions: FAIR implementation for NI4OS-Europe providers" which was co-organized by NI4OS-Europe and OntoCommons on the 29th of April 2022.

The 4th KExS meeting was organized on the 10th of May but then cancelled due to the small number of participants. The 5th meeting was organized on the 5th of July 2022. The 6th meeting was held on the 21st of July 2022 and was internal with participants belonging to OntoCommons only as well as the 7th meeting (1st of September 2022) which was a preparatory meeting for the 8th.

The last meeting was hosted on the 9th of September 2022. In this meeting NI4SO-Europe presented the plan of the future workshop "Becoming part of EOSC: learn how to prepare your services" planned for the 18th of October 2022, and co-organized in collaboration with OntoCommons and TU Wien.

4.4.3 The workshop "Becoming part of EOSC: learn how to prepare your services"

NI4OS-Europe in collaboration with OntoCommons and TU Wien, on the 18th of October 2022 organized the workshop "Becoming Part of EOSC: learn how to prepare your services".

The goal of this event was to inform the TU Wien researchers and other stakeholders about the European Open Science Cloud policies, use cases from the EOSC Catalogue and practical steps that enable services to be onboarded to its trusted, federated environment.

The ultimate vision of EOSC is to develop the "Web of FAIR data and services". The European Commission supports EOSC realisation aiming, among other things, to simplify cross-country and interdisciplinary access and interoperability in European research outputs that will increase innovation and market competition. Having services and data in EOSC enhances collaboration and visibility of intellectual works leading to a better flow of scientific information that reaches wider audiences and gets more citations. By being part of EOSC, services are employed with best practices to support Open and FAIR research that is a prerequisite in the European Research Area, thus securing researchers' competences and compliance with EU Open Science requirements.

The event was supported by the NI4OS-Europe project which designed the workflows and provides the tools for the onboarding of services to EOSC in the South East European region. Complementary, the OntoCommons project highlighted the work and best practices for ontologies in EOSC.

The event had such a structure so that by its end, participants were able to 1. navigate around and use the NI4OS-Europe catalogue 2. know the different steps and procedures relevant to onboarding their services to the EOSC Catalogue, 3. use new tools to comply

with the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboard their services to the EOSC Catalogue have their questions answered.

The program of the event can be found on the relevant webpage:
<https://forschungsdaten.at/en/fair-data-austria/materials/eosc-preparing-services/>

5 Actions of the NI4OS-Europe group of experts on metadata, ontologies and semantics

This group was formed and has taken place as an activity outside of the project DoA, yet complementing the work performed with onboarding of NI4OS-Europe services (WP3-5), establishing collaborations with other projects (WP7) and training the consortium and their respective local communities (WP6).

During the course of the first months of the NI4OS-Europe and communication with other INFRA-EOSC5b projects, it was recognized that further support was needed with the adoption of the FAIR principles, particularly on the technical aspects of metadata and semantics for the NI4OS-Europe service providers and researchers.

The new activity of the Metadata, Ontologies and Semantics Experts Group was introduced in December 2020. It aimed to clearly articulate best practices for FAIR implementation and provide guidance on integrations and/or alterations that are necessary for enhancing existing services or new services that are onboarded to EOSC via the NI4OS-Europe pre-production environment. The activity mobilized experts of the NI4OS-Europe consortium affiliated organizations' workforce from different domains and created a space where requirements were collected, discussed, and collectively addressed in the form of webinars, surveys and reports. The experts supporting this activity are the following (Table 5):

Name	Organization	Expertise
Valentina Vassallo	CYI	DCH & Crossdisciplinary semantics
Zoe Cournia	BRFAA	Life Science Metadata Schemas
Agiatis Benardou	ATHENA	Semantics on Arts and Humanities
Vicky Liakopoulou	UNI. of OXFORD	Metadata on Digital Humanities
Georgios Artopoulos	CYI	Architecture and DCH Metadata Schemas
Branko Marovic	UoB	ORDM
Adam Szaldobagyi	UD	Expert on several metadata schemas and Ontologies

Table 5: The names, institutions and areas of expertise of the members of the NI4OS-Europe Group of Experts on Metadata, Ontologies and Semantics

To offer visibility to the group activities, a webpage was created with the support of WP7 Dissemination. The dedicated experts group page can be found in the project's website: <https://ni4os.eu/expert-working-groups/>. A screenshot of the website is shown in Figure 23.

It contains an overview of what the activity is about, who are the experts (names, photos and short bios), and how they have worked together, linking to events and results.

Figure 23: A screenshot from the webpage dedicated to NI4OS-Europe Group of Experts on Metadata, Ontologies and Semantics

Two main events were organised by the group in collaboration with other projects, namely FAIRsFAIR and Ontocommons. Both were concerned with and linked to requirements elicitation via engaging in discussions with service providers and exchanging knowledge on the practical implementation of metadata, ontologies and semantics, also outside the NI4OS-Europe consortium. They offered bi-directoral ways of communicating the project results to the EOSC and NI4OS-Europe stakeholders, coupled with informing about methods, tools and use cases on those subjects, and collecting feedback and demand that later shaped the group’s actions.

In chronological order, the events are the following (Table 6):

Date	Venue/ Occasion	Title	URL of material
21 st September 2021	OSFair collaborative workshop with FAIRsFAIR	Speaking FAIR Implementation: Moving from recommendation to supporting practical implementation of service providers	https://zenodo.org/record/5547916#.Y8VJYnZBy5e
29 th April 2022	NI4OS-Europe Webinar with Ontocommons	Community Support Discussions: FAIR implementation for NI4OS-Europe providers	https://zenodo.org/record/6531749#.Y8VQ4HZBy5c

Table 6: A table with the events organized within the scope of NI4OS-Europe Group of Experts on Metadata, Ontologies and Semantics

Particularly, a survey was conducted inside the NI4OS-Europe consortium before the OSFAIR workshop to collect information about capabilities, current practices followed as

well as report challenges in applying the FAIR principles for metadata and semantics. The questions posed to respondents are found below:

Survey Questions:

Section A - Basic information

- Type of service (in NI4OS-Europe)
- Type of service in RDM lifecycle (eg analytics, storage, etc?)
- Area of expertise of the participant

Section B - Metadata and semantics

- Are there concrete data workflows in place to enable interoperability? (Yes/No)
 - Conditional: what activities/tasks do they support?
- Do you know / have you used semantics?
- What semantics do you use?
- Metadata standards available in the field
- Do you use any metadata schema?
- Types of metadata used (descriptive, technical, legal, etc)

Section C - FAIR principles

- How familiar are you with the FAIR principles? (likert scale : 1-5)
- What kind of challenges do you face? (implementation phase, design of FAIR, interoperability, etc)

Additionally, in the context of the OSFAIR workshop, a menti was developed that gathered useful information for the practices of the EOSC community of stakeholders. The results of the menti can be found here: <https://zenodo.org/record/5534279#.Y8ViQnZBy5c>.

The experts group utilized these inputs to design customized advice and support respondent services and interested stakeholders. Today, there is an ongoing activity to consolidate this information and information from meetings with service providers into a report of the findings and guidance towards practical implementation of metadata, ontologies and semantics. Below, we summarize some primary results covering the challenges of this activity:

Area	Challenges
Interoperability	On the data level (see also ontologies); restrictive semantics and mandatory metadata
Reproducibility	Availability System architecture, compiler and library version; complex codes and HPC resources
Metadata	Less emphasis and examples provided for other than descriptive metadata; lack of confidence to choose from the existing metadata standards; time consuming research on the metadata documentation to find machine actionable standards; domains lack of metadata standards for certain activities
Ontologies	Controlled vocabularies and ontologies should be clearly defined, taxonomies; lack of confidence to choose from the existing ontologies; domains lack of ontologies; interoperability across ontologies
Standards	Lack of standardization; knowledge of the tools to use and technicalities to expect
Training and awareness	Lack of awareness; lack of comparison across tools and methods / compatibility examples
Technical implementation	Integration with repository (technical limitations of repository software); heterogeneity and inhomogeneity
Other	Multilingualism; multidisciplinary

Table 7: Primary results from the survey, covering the challenges of this activity

5.1 *Foundations for a new metadata schema about "HeritageBuiltEnvironment"*

The next step in the development of built heritage digitization methods should focus in expanding the scope of study beyond the single built heritage structure and allowing deeper understanding and interdisciplinary interpretation of its condition and performance within its topographical context and the surrounding built environment. This could become a reality today by means of the advancements in digital tools, remote sensing, algorithms and computation prowess of hardware available to researchers. Data interoperability and re-use, in the context of the FAIR principles, can only be achieved through the semantic enrichment of metadata. For these metadata to become interoperable though, we need the appropriate ontologies and schemata. Hence this action proposes the creation of a new schema extension in Protégé that would enable linking the relevant to cultural heritage of our historic cities multi-modal and multi-discipline datasets, e.g., 3D models, IFC, historical descriptions, environmental data.

Results:

A document that describes a series of metadata schemas such as bibliographic documentation or geoinformatics, that are required to be added to the BIM model in order to meet the specifications of a CIDOC CRM based on ISO standards ISO 21127:2014. The result of this action is the description of a new metadata schema in CIDOC-CRM, as an extension of the CARARE 2.0 metadata schema, which is based on MIDAS (English Heritage Listed Building System) schema for built heritage and monuments.

The results will be published on Zenodo and are also disseminated to the relevant digital humanities communities through the DARIAH ERIC [WG on Digital Practices for the Study of Urban Heritage](#).

A process graph of the metadata structure by Level of Detail (LOD100-400) is provided in Figure 24.

Figure 24: A process graph of the metadata structured by Level of Detail (LOD100-400)

6 Conclusions

This deliverable captures the main activities of Task 6.3 and provides the implementation strategy and actions taken for the EOSC service uptake and FAIR uptake in the communities.

Guidelines and recommendations of task 6.3 were aiming at supporting the NI4OS-Europe work to promote EOSC and FAIR and establish sustainable national open science cloud initiatives. The stakeholders' analysis through the survey findings (WP2) were able to provide the necessary information in order to be able to identify and reach the most appropriate audiences. In accordance to that, EOSC Promoters were able to identify and reach their local relevant stakeholders.

The achievements of EOSC Promoters can be considered as a success story considering the fact that a lot of activities took place in the Pandemic era and the fact that other projects adopted the idea of EOSC ambassadors (e.g. EOSC Pillar).

As NI4OS-Europe is one the INFRAEOSC-5b projects, the close collaboration with other related projects was considered essential in order to achieve a Europe-wide community that supported the EOSC and FAIR uptake and created a greater link to EOSC and stakeholders.